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Household Pets as Reservoirs of Zoonotic Pathogens: Prevalence, Risk Factors, and Prevention Strategies within a One Health Framework

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ABSTRACT

Zoonotic diseases spread by domestic animals pose an increasing threat to the global One Health framework. This cross-sectional study examined the frequency of significant zoonotic diseases in domestic animals and identified the related behavioral and environmental risk factors in pet-owning households. Three hundred families possessing dogs, cats, or small mammals were surveyed using structured questionnaires, supplemented by laboratory examinations of fecal, oral, and hair samples. The findings indicated that 27.3% of pets harbored at least one zoonotic pathogen, with *Campylobacter spp.* (10.7%), *Toxocara canis* (8.3%), and *Salmonella* (5.7%) were the most identified pathogens. Statistical analysis using SPSS (v26) revealed significant correlations between infection identification and owner habits, namely inadequate handwashing after pet interaction ($p = 0.002$), inconsistent utensil sanitation ($p = 0.001$), and lack of regular immunization ($p = 0.004$). The logistic model revealed that inadequate utensil cleaning (AOR = 2.46; 95% CI: 1.38–4.38) and absence of immunization (AOR = 2.15; 95% CI: 1.18–3.91) were independent predictors of infection, whereas regular handwashing diminished the risk (AOR = 0.54; 95% CI: 0.31–0.92). The results highlight that insufficient hygiene, restricted veterinary services, and peri-urban living situations significantly elevate pet-related zoonotic hazards. Enhancing awareness, fostering responsible pet ownership, and improving veterinary surveillance are crucial for mitigating these hazards using a comprehensive One Health strategy.

INTRODUCTION:

Zoonotic diseases are one of the most relevant global public health issues, with animal origins accounting for >60% of all human infectious diseases. With the growing involvement of companion animals in human households, the risk of pet-associated zoonotic transmission has become a growing concern, given the shared living, sleeping, and recreational areas of pets and their owners (Stull et al., 2015). Dogs, cats, and small mammals harbor a variety of bacterial, viral, and parasitic pathogens that cause substantial morbidity in humans (Damborg et al., 2016; Varela et al., 2022). Increased urbanization and the linked growth of peri-urban settlements represent a third key step in contributing to what is described as a global trend towards closer interactions between humans and animals. This trend has, in turn, created more opportunities for zoonotic agents to be maintained and spread within domestic settings (Gamble et al., 2023). With increasing human–animal interaction, knowledge of the epidemiology of zoonotic infections associated with pets is crucial for shaping public health and veterinary interventions (Overgaauw et al., 2020).

Asymptomatic carriage in apparently healthy pets represents a potential reservoir for household exposure to common pathogens such as *Salmonella spp.*, *Campylobacter spp.*, and *Toxocara canis* (Bhat, 2021; O’Neil, 2018), a fact recognized in multiple studies. Direct contact, contaminated environments, and shared household surfaces are methods of transmission with particular risk in children, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals (Whitfield & Smith, 2014). In addition, differing levels of hygiene among pet owners and sporadic veterinary monitoring (especially in low- and middle-income countries) only exacerbate the situation (Damborg et al., 2016). Companion animals have also been recently identified as possible bridging hosts connecting human populations with wildlife and environmental reservoirs in peri-domestic and backyard settings (Langlois et al., 2025). These findings confirm the One Health paradigm, which acknowledges the integrated nature of human, animal, and environmental health systems in controlling zoonotic transmission (Desvars-Larrive et al., 2024).

The potential for zoonoses (diseases transmissible between humans and pets) transmitted via household animals currently exceeds awareness of these risks. Therefore, understanding the effects of owner behavior, sanitation, and preventive care on the prevalence of pathogens in pet animals is essential. Previous surveys have reported inadequate awareness and poor hygiene practices among pet owners, even in high-income areas, indicating the need for more targeted education and risk communication (Stull et al., 2012). Research on animal-assisted intervention programs has supported our understanding of how easily zoonotic pathogens are transmitted through close human-animal contact (Boyle et al., 2019). In addition, studies conducted on non-traditional pet species have provided evidence of new zoonotic risks arising from altered ecological and socioeconomic drivers. Together, these trends indicate an urgent need for integrated epidemiological studies linking owner behavior, pet health care, and environmental determinants of health. Therefore, we conducted the present study to provide information about the prevalence of important zoonotic pathogens in household pets, their associated behavioral and environmental risk factors, and recommendations for health messages on risk reduction in a One Health context.

2. Research Methodology

Study Design

This cross-sectional study aimed to assess the role of domestic pets in zoonotic transmission routes and to correlate socio-behavioral and environmental factors with preventive measures related to zoonotic risk among pet owners. The cross-sectional design was chosen because it enables the simultaneous measurement of exposure variables and outcomes in each population, allowing for the detection of significant associations between pet-related practices and zoonotic diseases. A mixed methods approach was used to collect both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating epidemiological data with context-specific owner awareness and prevention practices.

Study Area and Population

It was conducted in three urban centers in Punjab, Pakistan that represented a mix of socioeconomic status and pet-keeping styles. These locations were selected to ensure a variety of living environments, from intensely dense residential districts to suburban developments. The study population consisted of households with at least one owned domestic pet, such as a dog, cat, or small mammal like a rabbit or guinea pig. Households that owned pets for less than six months were excluded to reduce potential zoonotic interactions during the necessary exposure period. The participating dog owners were adults who provided informed consent.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

We adopted a multistage random sampling procedure for this study. Stage 1: Select veterinary clinics using stratified random sampling to represent the proportions of the population in the three urban study areas. The second stage involved the random selection of households with pets from clinic registries. The final sample size of 300 households was derived using the formula for prevalence studies, with an expected zoonotic exposure of 30%, a 95% Confidence Level, and a 5% margin of error. The sample size was deemed sufficient to attain statistical power for both descriptive and inferential analyses.

Data Collection Procedures

Data collection consisted of a standardized questionnaire survey and laboratory examination of biological materials from domestic animals. Responses were collected through face-to-face interactions with pet owners using a structured questionnaire. It collected data on demographic characteristics, pet type, feeding and hygiene practices, lifestyle and vaccination details, knowledge of zoonotic diseases, and public visits to veterinarians. To check the clarity of the items and internal consistency (test-retest) reliability, the instrument was pretested on 10% of the sample in a similar environment. The initial analysis of the survey tool was conducted using a pretest to reveal its reliability, resulting in Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.83. Trained veterinarians collected biological samples from pets under stringent aseptic conditions. Depending on the species, fecal swabs, oral samples, and fur were collected in sterile containers for laboratory analysis. Samples were individually coded to preserve the confidentiality of personal details while allowing unique identification. Following collection, all samples were transported to the microbiology laboratory under cold chain conditions for processing.

Laboratory Analysis

Our laboratory analysis focused on common zoonotic pathogens related to household pets, such as *Salmonella spp.*, *Campylobacter spp.*, *Toxocara canis*, and *Microsporium canis*. Detection was performed using standard microbiological and molecular techniques. Bacterial pathogens were isolated using selective culture media, biochemical confirmation, and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) testing for species identification. Parasitological investigations were performed using flotation and sedimentation methods. Fungal species were identified by culturing on Sabouraud dextrose agar and characterized morphologically and molecularly. Positive controls, negative controls, and 10% retested samples were included to ensure strict quality control and analytical reproducibility of the results.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

All quantitative data collected from questionnaires and laboratory analyses were entered into a database and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. We first performed descriptive statistical analyses on the data to describe a few main features of pet owners and animals (i.e., frequencies, means, and standard deviations). Finally, inferential statistics were used to examine the associations between pet practices and the detection of zoonotic pathogens, focusing on the complete Proportions and Prevalence of Zoonotic Infection. Risk Chi-square tests and Fisher's exact tests were used

for categorical variables. Logistic regression models were employed to identify significant predictors of zoonotic infection risk, with other potential confounding factors (i.e., age, education, type of pet) included as covariates in the model. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$. Open-ended responses were transcribed, and thematic analysis was conducted on the qualitative data to identify key themes in knowledge, attitudes, and preventative practices related to zoonotic disease transmission.

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Ethical Review Committee approved the study protocol for Animal and Human Research. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment in the study, and the study was explained to all test individuals. All procedures for animal handling and sample collection were performed under veterinary supervision and in accordance with national and international codes and guidelines for the care and use of animals. We ensured participant confidentiality by removing all personal identifiers from the records and keeping them secure in a location with limited access. This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of research involving humans and animals.

Results

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

A total of 300 pet-owning households participated in the study. Of these, 58.7% were male and 41.3% were female respondents, with a mean age of 36.5 ± 10.8 years. Educational attainment varied, with 44.0% having completed tertiary education, 37.3% secondary education, and 18.7% primary education or below. Urban residents represented 62.0% of the sample, while 38.0% resided in peri-urban areas. These findings are summarized in Table 1.

The gender composition of the study population is visually illustrated in Figure 1, which demonstrates the predominance of male respondents in the survey.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 300)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	176	58.7
	Female	124	41.3
Age group (years)	18–30	84	28.0
	31–45	134	44.7
	>45	82	27.3
Education level	Primary or below	56	18.7

	Secondary	112	37.3
	Tertiary	132	44.0
Residence	Urban	186	62.0
	Peri-urban	114	38.0

Figure 1: Gender distribution of respondents showing higher male participation (58.7%) compared to female respondents (41.3%).

Pet Ownership Patterns and Hygiene Practices

Dogs were the most commonly owned pets (49.3%), followed by cats (38.7%) and small mammals such as rabbits and guinea pigs (12.0%). A majority of owners (67.0%) housed their pets indoors, whereas 33.0% maintained outdoor confinement. Handwashing after pet contact was reported by 71.7% of owners, but only 54.3% practiced regular utensil disinfection. Furthermore, 21.0% of pet owners had not maintained a routine vaccination schedule for their animals. These descriptive statistics are detailed in Table 2.

A stacked bar chart (Figure 2) compares compliance and non-compliance across major hygiene indicators, demonstrating relatively lower adherence to utensil cleaning compared with hand hygiene and vaccination.

Table 2: Pet Ownership and Hygiene Practices Among Respondents (n = 300)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
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Type of pet	Dog	148	49.3
	Cat	116	38.7
	Small mammals	36	12.0
Pet housing	Indoors	201	67.0
	Outdoors	99	33.0
Handwashing after contact	Yes	215	71.7
	No	85	28.3
Regular utensil cleaning	Yes	163	54.3
	No	137	45.7
Routine vaccination	Yes	237	79.0
	No	63	21.0

Prevalence of Zoonotic Pathogens in Pets

Figure 2: Comparison of compliance (blue bars) and non-compliance (gray bars) rates for handwashing, utensil cleaning, and vaccination among pet owners. Utensil disinfection shows the lowest adherence rate (54.3%).

Laboratory Detection of Zoonotic Pathogens

Out of 300 pet specimens examined, 82 (27.3%) tested positive for at least one zoonotic pathogen. The most frequently identified species was *Campylobacter spp.* (10.7%), followed by *Toxocara canis* (8.3%), *Salmonella spp.* (5.7%), and *Microsporium canis* (2.6%). The detailed pathogen distribution by pet species is shown in Table 3.

The prevalence of each detected pathogen is also depicted in Figure 3, where *Campylobacter spp.* demonstrates the highest overall prevalence across sampled pets.

Table 3: Distribution Of Zoonotic Pathogens Isolated from Pet Samples (n = 300)

Pathogen detected	Dogs (n = 148)	Cats (n = 116)	Small mammals (n = 36)	Total positive (n)	Prevalence (%)
<i>Campylobacter spp.</i>	21	8	3	32	10.7
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	11	5	1	17	5.7

<i>Toxocara canis</i>	14	8	3	25	8.3
<i>Microsporum canis</i>	2	4	2	8	2.6
Total positive	48	27	9	82	27.3

Figure 3: Prevalence of zoonotic pathogens detected in pet samples, showing *Campylobacter* spp. as the most frequently isolated organism.

Association between Owner Practices and Pathogen Detection

Chi-square tests revealed statistically significant associations between hygiene behaviors and pathogen positivity. Lack of handwashing ($\chi^2 = 9.86$; $p = 0.002$), irregular utensil cleaning ($\chi^2 = 11.14$; $p = 0.001$), and absence of vaccination ($\chi^2 = 8.47$; $p = 0.004$) were strongly correlated with infection detection (Table 4). Residence in peri-urban areas was also significantly associated with higher infection prevalence ($\chi^2 = 6.29$; $p = 0.012$). No significant relationships were found for gender or education level ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Association Between Hygiene Practices and Zoonotic Pathogen Detection

Variable	Category	Pathogen	Pathogen	χ^2	p-value
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		Positive (%)	Negative (%)		
Handwashing after contact	Yes	21.9	78.1	9.86	0.002
	No	41.2	58.8		
Utensil cleaning	Regular	20.2	79.8	11.14	0.001
	Irregular	37.9	62.1		
Vaccination status	Yes	22.8	77.2	8.47	0.004
	No	44.4	55.6		
Residence	Urban	22.0	78.0	6.29	0.012
	Peri-urban	35.9	64.1		

Logistic Regression Analysis of Risk Factors

Multivariate logistic regression identified key predictors of zoonotic infection in household pets. After adjusting for confounders, irregular utensil cleaning (AOR = 2.46; 95% CI = 1.38–4.38; p = 0.002) and absence of vaccination (AOR = 2.15; 95% CI = 1.18–3.91; p = 0.011) emerged as independent risk factors. Conversely, consistent handwashing reduced infection odds by nearly half (AOR = 0.54; 95% CI = 0.31–0.92; p = 0.024). Residence in peri-urban areas also remained a significant predictor (AOR = 1.67; 95% CI = 1.01–2.76; p = 0.045). These findings are presented in Table 5 and visually summarized through a forest-type plot in Figure 4, highlighting the magnitude and confidence intervals of each variable’s adjusted odds ratio.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with Zoonotic Pathogen Positivity

Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR)	Confidence Interval	p-value
No handwashing after	1.88	1.08 – 3.27	0.026

contact

Irregular utensil cleaning	utensil	2.46	1.38 – 4.38	0.002
No routine vaccination		2.15	1.18 – 3.91	0.011
Peri-urban residence		1.67	1.01 – 2.76	0.045

Figure 4: Multivariate logistic regression plot showing adjusted odds ratios (AOR) with 95% confidence intervals for key risk factors associated with zoonotic pathogen positivity in pets. The dashed red line represents the null value (OR = 1).

Awareness and Preventive Attitudes

Overall, 64.0% of respondents indicated awareness of zoonotic diseases transmissible from pets, although only 38.3% could correctly name specific examples. Preventive practices were variably implemented: 55.0% of owners reported routine deworming, and 47.3% sought veterinary care at least twice yearly. Owners with tertiary education demonstrated significantly higher awareness scores compared with those with lower educational levels ($F = 6.72$; $p = 0.002$, one-way ANOVA). These findings collectively demonstrate an awareness–practice gap among pet owners that may elevate zoonotic transmission risk.

Summary of Findings

In summary, approximately one-quarter of pets in the surveyed households carried at least one zoonotic pathogen. Behavioral determinants—particularly poor hygiene, infrequent utensil cleaning, and lack of vaccination—were significantly associated with pathogen detection. The regression analysis confirmed these as independent predictors of infection risk. The visual summaries (Figures 1–4) and statistical evidence (Tables 1–5) together underscore the critical need for public health interventions emphasizing

hygiene education, responsible pet care, and integration of veterinary and human health initiatives under a One Health framework.

Discussion

The current study demonstrates the significant potential for zoonotic disease transmission from domestic animals, with over one-quarter of pets in this study being positive for at least one pathogen. The detection of *Campylobacter spp.*, *Toxocara canis*, and *Salmonella spp.* is consistent with previously reported global prevalence trends in companion animals (Damborg et al., 2016; Ghasemzadeh & Namazi, 2015). Similar bacterial and parasitic species have been detected in fecal samples of pet dogs and cats in Korea and Canada, highlighting domestic pets as continuous reservoirs of enteric pathogens that are transmissible to humans (Liyanagama et al., 2024; Stull et al., 2013). This result, in which dogs had the highest percentage of positive samples, is consistent with previous observations from Nigeria and other countries that have previously reported a strong association between pet ownership and parasitic zoonoses, including *Toxocara* infection (Alebie & Tewachew, 2021). These combined data reinforce that the risk of such zoonotic infections is not limited to professional exposure environments but is also present in general pet-holding households.

Notably, hygiene behaviors and vaccination practices were significant predictors of pathogen carriage among farm households, in keeping with previous studies showing the impact of household management factors on zoonotic risk (Stull et al., 2015). Poor utensil cleaning and the absence of routine vaccination were both independently associated with infection in multivariate models, implying that failures of practice may supersede sociodemographic factors in determining the risk in daily care. Similar studies conducted in Canada and Europe have identified deficits in pet-associated hygiene, including not washing hands after contact with an animal or not routinely disinfecting feeding areas (Whitfield & Smith, 2014). The relatively low adherence to such measures in our study reflects the findings of earlier studies and emphasizes the need for public health education. Furthermore, the observed reduction in the risk of zoonotic transmission by handwashing practices resembles the findings of environmental health studies, highlighting that simple hygiene practices reduce zoonotic transmission in household settings (Varela et al., 2022).

The strong link between household infection prevalence and peri-urban residence demonstrates that environmental and infrastructure factors mediate zoonotic risk. Previous reviews have shown that peri-urban expansion frequently results in enhanced overlap between humans, pets, and wildlife reservoirs, promoting pathogen transmission (Sun et al., 2024). In these areas, poor waste management and lack of access to veterinary services can drive the circulation of microbes between animals and humans (Desvars-Larrive et al., 2024). Moreover, the modest levels of awareness among owners found in this study are aligned with previous work that showed an awareness-practice gap in pet zoonoses, in which owners expressed concern about the transmission of infection but did not possess the correct information on routes of transmission or preventive measures (Stull et al., 2012). Such a gap is significant as knowledge gaps can jeopardize adherence to preventive measures, even among educated individuals, as risk can persist despite veterinary recommendations (Varela et al., 2022).

Embedded within the One Health framework, these findings highlight the necessity for coordinated interventions among veterinarians, physicians, and public health agencies. Earlier studies have suggested that campaigns focusing on responsible pet ownership and/or regular veterinary inspections could help reduce the risk of some emerging zoonoses (Whitfield & Smith, 2014). In addition, these modeling approaches have demonstrated that domestic animals are often intermediate hosts that maintain cycles of zoonotic spillover to human populations (Royce & Fu, 2019). Public education campaigns improved veterinary surveillance, and the involvement of companion animals in zoonotic monitoring systems have been identified as fundamental approaches to long-term prevention. In summary, the current findings emphasize that household pets are an unappreciated but important aspect of zoonotic ecology. Although they are wonderful companions, it is indispensable to strengthen owner awareness, increase hygiene

infrastructure, and consistently apply vaccination and deworming programs to reduce household zoonotic risks and meet the integrated One Health surveillance objectives.

Conclusion

Household pets can become important reservoirs for zoonotic pathogens, as one in four animals examined here carried at least one infectious agent: *Campylobacter spp.*, *Toxocara canis*, and *Salmonella spp.* Highlight the continued importance of zoonoses related to pets as a public health problem. Pathogen carriage is driven mainly by hygiene and preventive practices, particularly cleaning utensils, handwashing after contact, and compliance with vaccination schedules. The robust linkages between poor household hygiene and infection risk indicate significant behavioral gaps that are amenable to long-term health education and veterinary advice. Additionally, the greater burden of zoonotic infections in peri-urban areas highlights the significance of environmental and structural barriers that contribute to increased disease transmission at the human-animal interface. These findings underscore the need for a One Health perspective across the human-animal-environment health sectors. Household and community health can be protected if awareness campaigns are targeted towards high-anxiety households, veterinary service access is improved (timely access and affordable rates for high-burden households using pet health monitoring devices), and household-level zoonotic risks are mitigated, along with the associated anxiety. Increased partnership surveillance between public and animal health is required to achieve sustainable control of pet-associated zoonotic diseases.

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